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PERSPECTIVES OF WORLD SCIENCE AND EDUCATION

**ABSTRACTS OF VIII INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE
APRIL 22-24, 2020**

**OSAKA
2020**

PERSPECTIVES OF WORLD SCIENCE AND EDUCATION

Abstracts of VIII International Scientific and Practical Conference

Osaka, Japan

22-24 April 2020

Osaka, Japan

2020

UDC 001.1

BBK 79

The 8th International scientific and practical conference “Perspectives of world science and education” (April 22-24, 2020) CPN Publishing Group, Osaka, Japan. 2020. 980 p.

ISBN 978-4-9783419-8-3

The recommended citation for this publication is:

Ivanov I. Analysis of the phaunistic composition of Ukraine // Perspectives of world science and education. Abstracts of the 8th International scientific and practical conference. CPN Publishing Group. Osaka, Japan. 2020. Pp. 21-27. URL: <http://sci-conf.com.ua>.

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UDC 616.1; 616.8

**STUDY OF RISK FACTORS OF CEREBRAL STROKES ACCORDING TO
THE DATA OF REGIONAL REGISTERS AND NATIONAL SERVICES OF
MEDICAL STATISTICS**

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Abstract. Using the registers of patients with cerebral stroke, the frequency of occurrence of risk factors in various populations was studied. A comparison of the averaged data was carried out, followed by a comparison with the data of national and international prospective studies of stroke risk factors. The main (“significant”) risk factors remain unchanged in any population. Their corrections are attributed to 2/3 of the success in reducing mortality from strokes (1/3 refers to the success of therapy).

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, cerebral stroke, risk factors, registers of stroke patients, epidemiological studies, state medical statistics.

The WHO defines a stroke “as a rapidly developing clinical syndrome of focal (or generalized with subarachnoid bleeding) impaired brain function lasting more than 24 hours or leading to death in the absence of obvious causes of this syndrome, except for a violation of the blood supply” [1].

Numerous studies of risk factors for cerebral strokes have allowed us to come to a unified model for recording all cases of the disease in the form of regional registers in which are fixed: data on the type of stroke are recorded for each patient (primary or repeated, ischemic or hemorrhagic, with hemorrhage in the brain tissue or under the meninges), symptoms, laboratory and instrumental studies results, risk factors identified in each patient, disease dynamics, concomitant diseases and conditions, treatment regimens, rehabilitation, prognosis. Entering data into the register is a doctor's report on the work done, allows him to choose the best treatment regimen after analyzing the data on treatment of his own patients, patients of his medical institution, service or region. The registers of stroke patients allow conducting epidemiological studies, planning and adjusting selected treatment regimens, prevention programs, comparing regions and countries with each other, and conducting cohort prospective studies [2].

To assess the situation of stroke incidence in the population and to monitor the dynamics allows epidemiology, which evaluates primarily such indicators [3]:

- incidence – the number of new cases of stroke per year, calculated per 1000 inhabitants;
- hospitalized morbidity – the frequency of all cases of diseases recorded in patients in a hospital for a year, calculated per 1000 inhabitants;
- mortality – the number of stroke cases per year ending fatally, calculated per 1000 inhabitants;
- mortality – the percentage of deaths from a stroke relative to all reported cases of the disease (in percent).

In the individual plan, the most informative is the analysis of the identified risk factors, the construction of the risk factor profile and its comparison with the average indicators of the corresponding age group, taking into account the gender and type of stroke [4]. A global study of stroke risk factors in 188 countries for the period 1990-2013 shows [5; 6] that the occurrence of stroke is associated with a combination of factors that are constant, but constant in the list: behavioral (tobacco smoking, poor nutrition, low physical activity), metabolic (hypertension, high body mass index,

fasting plasma hyperglycemia, hypercholesterolemia, low glomerular filtration rate) and environmental factors (air pollution, plumbum). Rough averaging of data from several studies of stroke risk factors in the regional registers of the Russian Federation and Ukraine (see table 1) allows us to test the hypothesis that, regardless of the population, the main risk factors for stroke do not change, they correspond to the global and Ukrainian ones.

In this table, kitchen salt (sodium chloride) abuse means exceeding the amount recommended by WHO of 5 grams per day per person, and alcohol abuse – exceeding the amount of 30-60 grams of pure ethyl alcohol (absolute alcohol) per day per person, in accordance with various recommendations [9; 10]. The data obtained take into account the ratio of the types of primary stroke: ischemic / hemorrhagic with hemorrhage in the brain tissue / subarachnoid hemorrhage as 0.8 / 0.15 / 0.05 [1].

The identified “significant” risk factors have a significant impact on the development of stroke, occur in each or in most populations, and when eliminated, the risk of stroke is minimized.

The data of the Russian registers were better systematized and described. In the studies of Starodubtseva O.S. [3; 7] used the data of 4 years of monitoring 9520 patients with acute cerebrovascular accident using the epidemiological monitoring information system "Register of stroke patients" (RF Certificate of State Registration No. 2010612630 of April 15, 2010). In the studies of Nikulin S.Yu. et al. (2018) [8] analyzed 152 cases of ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke in the urban population of the city of Krasnoyarsk (Eastern Siberia), who were treated in 2014 at the neurological center of the Federal Clinical Hospital "Siberian Clinical Center of the Federal Biomedical Agency". The source [11] summarized research data in 14 countries over 4 years (2015-2018) relative to patients aged 20-64 years.

Table 1

The main risk factors for cerebral stroke and their detection in male and female of various age groups in sample studies of regional registers for 2016-2018

Risk factor	Years of research	Literary source [No.]	The number of patients observed, thousand	Age	The maximum and minimum frequency of occurrence,% (rounded to integers)		
					male	female	total
Hypodynamia	2012-2016	3,7	9.5	15-70+	48	35	41-56
Dyslipidemia	2012-2018	3,7,11	9.5	15-70+	7-66	44-73	60-72
Atherosclerosis	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.6	15-70+	40	24	61-72
Salt abuse	2014-2018	11	14	20-64	43	38	39
Hyperglycemia (diabetes)	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.6	15-70+	4-14	4-26	7-19
Poor nutrition	2012-2016	3,7	9.5	15-70+	34	31	27-35
Obesity	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.5	15-70+	41-58	14-49	38-70
Arterial hypertension	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.6	15-70+	55-96	38-97	94-97
Coronary artery disease including myocardial infarction in anamnesis	2012-2018	3,7,8,11	9.6	15-70+	7-11	6-11	13-80
Transient cerebrovascular accident / stroke in anamnesis	2012-2016	3,7	9.6	15-70+	1-15	2-27	12-40
Atrial fibrillation	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.5	15-70+	39	33	28-43
Thromboembolic conditions	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.6	15-70+	4-24	3-34	7-31
Tobacco smoking	2014-2018	11	36	20-64	14	21	20
Alcohol abuse	2012-2016	3,7,8	9.5	15-70+	31-71	7-36	36-79
Oral contraceptives	2012-2016	3,7	9.5	15-70+	31	7	17-29
Burdened heredity	2012-2018	3,7,11	26.2	15-70+	-	0.4-0.8	0.4-0.8
	2014-2018	8	2.15	20-60	3	5	8

The prevalence in Ukraine of the most significant risk factors for death from noncommunicable diseases, averaged by age, including cardiovascular diseases, is

shown in Table 2 [12], and the risk of death at the age of 30-70 years from noncommunicable diseases according to 2016 for male is 35%, for female – 16%, total – 25%.

Table 2

Selected trends in risk factors for death from noncommunicable diseases for people aged 15+ according to WHO studies 2016-2018

Risk factor	Year of study	Age, years	Frequency of occurrence, %		
			Males	Females	Total
Hypodynamia (physical inactivity)	2016	18+	19	22	21
Tobacco use	2016	15+	48	11	27
Unregulated arterial hypertension	2015	18+	35	30	32
Hyperglycemia	2014	18+	8	10	9
Obesity	2016	18+	23	28	26
		10-19 (teenagers)	8	4	6

A comparison of the five “significant” risk factors for cerebral stroke in our study with the data from the Ukraine State Medical Statistics Service provided by WHO in 2016 shows a coincidence in terms of tobacco smoking, hypertension, obesity and hyperglycemia, but they differ in terms of physical inactivity. However, all five factors are those whose frequency is maximum in both data sets. This allows us to conclude: the hypothesis of the widespread prevalence of the main "significant" risk factors for stroke is confirmed.

REFERENCES

1. Stulin I.D. Stroke from the point of view of evidence-based medicine / I.D. Stulin, R.S. Musin, Yu.B. Belousov // Qualitative clinical practice. – 2003. – No. 4. – P. 110-118. URL: <https://www.clinvest.ru/jour/article/viewFile/303/382.pdf> (In Russian)
2. Neurology: national handbook / ed. E.I. Gusev, A.N. Konovalova, V.I. Skvortsova. – 2nd ed., rev. and suppl. – M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2018. – In 2 vol., vol. 1. – 880 p. – ISBN 978-5-9704-4143-5. URL: <http://www.geotar.ru/lots/NF0004381.html> (In Russian)

3. Starodubtseva O.S. Analysis of the incidence of stroke using information technology / O.S. Starodubtseva, S.V. Begicheva // Fundamental research. – 2012. – No. 8-2. – P. 424-427. URL: <http://www.fundamental-research.ru/en/article/view?id=3038> (In Russian)
4. Gusev E.I. Epidemiology of stroke in Russia / E.I. Gusev, L.V. Skvortsova, L.V. Stakhovskaya // Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry. – 2003. – No. 9. – P. 114-118. (In Russian)
5. Feigin V.L. Global burden of stroke and risk factors in 188 countries, during 1990-2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013 / V.L. Feigin, G.A. Roth, M. Naghavi, [et al.] // Lancet Neurol. – 2016. – Vol. 15, No. 9. – P. 913-924. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(16\)30073-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(16)30073-4)
6. Kayerova E.V. Analysis of the main risk factors for stroke / E.V. Kayerova, N.S. Zhuravskaya, L.V. Matveeva [et al.] // Modern problems of science and education. – 2017. – No. 6. URL: <http://www.science-education.ru/en/article/view?id=27342> (In Russian)
7. Starodubtseva O.S. Assessment of stroke risk factors in industrial agglomeration / O.S. Starodubtseva // Medical-social and psychological aspects of the safety of industrial agglomerations: materials of the International scientific-practical conference (Yekaterinburg, February 16-17, 2016). – Yekaterinburg: UrFU, 2016. – P. 56-61. URL: http://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/38047/1/msip_2016_09.pdf (In Russian)
8. Nikulina S.Y. Differences in the Incidence of Major Risk Factors in Patients with Ischemic or Hemorrhagic Stroke in the Siberian Population / S.Y. Nikulina, A.A. Chernova, D.A. Nikulin, [et al.] // Rational Pharmacotherapy in Cardiology. – 2018. – Vol. 14, No. 4. – P. 509-514. DOI: 10.20996/1819-6446-2018-14-4-509-514 (In Russian)
9. Meshkova K.S. Risk factors and stroke prevention / K.S. Meshkova, V.V. Gudkova, L.V. Stakhovskaya // Journal "Zemsky Doctor". – 2013. – Vol. 19, No. 2. – P. 16-19. URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=19127995> (In Russian)

10. Lindroos L. How to drink alcohol // Addictionlink (Helsinki), October 19, 2006.
URL: <https://paihdelinkki.fi/en/bank-informacii/informacionnye-izdaniya/alkogol/kak-sleduet-upotreblyat-alkogol> (In Russian)
11. Risk factors and their interconnection with cardio-vascular diseases: Chapter 1 in: Guidelines for cardiology // Clinical guidelines “Compendium”. URL: <https://compendium.com.ua/clinical-guidelines/cardiology/section-4/glava-1-factory-riska-i-ih-vzaimosvyaz-s-serdechno-sosudistymi-zabolevaniyami> (In Russian)
12. Ukraine. Selected adult risk factor trends // World Health Organization, Global Health Observatory data. Noncommunicable Diseases Country Profiles, 2018 URL: https://www.who.int/nmh/countries/ukr_en.pdf

Cite as: [Ognev, V.A., Mishchenko, M.M., Mishchenko, A.N., Shevchenko, A.S. (2020) Study of risk factors of cerebral strokes according to the data of regional registers and national services of medical statistics. Perspectives of world science and education: Abstracts of the 8th International scientific and practical conference (Osaka, Japan, 2020, April 22-24). CPN Publishing Group (ISBN 978-4-9783419-8-3). Pp. 122-128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3766421>]

Цитируйте как: [Огнев, В.А., Мищенко, М.М., Мищенко, А.Н., Шевченко, А.С. (2020) Изучение факторов риска церебральных инсультов по данным региональных регистров и национальных служб медицинской статистики. Перспективы мировой науки и образования: Тезисы докладов 8-й Международной научно-практической конференции (Осака, Япония, 22-24 апреля 2020 года). Издательская группа CPN (ISBN 978-4-9783419-8-3). С. 122-128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3766421> (На английском)]

С помощью регистров больных церебральным инсультом изучена частота встречаемости факторов риска в различных популяциях. Проведено сравнение усредненных данных с последующим сравнением с данными национальных и международных проспективных исследований факторов риска инсульта. Основные («значимые») факторы риска остаются неизменными в любой популяции. Их коррекции приписывают 2/3 успеха снижения смертности от инсультов (1/3 относится к успехам терапии).

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, церебральный инсульт, факторы риска, регистры больных инсультами, эпидемиологические исследования, государственная медицинская статистика.